

RECENT ADVANCES IN NANOTECHNOLOGY-DRIVEN DRUG DEVELOPMENT: CLINICAL PROGRESS, REGULATORY EVOLUTION, AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

Nanotechnology has become a buzzword in pharmaceutical sciences and efforts are ongoing to extend its applications in various streams. Over the last two decades nanotechnology has dramatically influenced drug delivery research and several nanoscale carriers have been explored for improving therapeutic performance of drugs. Nanotechnology will affect our lives tremendously in very different fields, including medicine and pharmacy. Transfer of materials into nano-dimension changes their physical properties which were used in pharmaceutics to develop a new innovative formulation principles for poorly soluble drugs. Pharmaceutical nanotechnology is most innovative and highly specialized field, which will revolutionize the pharmaceutical industry in near future. In this review, a discussion was carried out on Current applications of nanotechnology in the development of nano-drug delivery systems like nanoparticles, solid lipid nanoparticles, nanocrystals, nanosuspensions and nanoemulsions. The ultimate goal of nanotechnology is to enhance the therapeutic efficacy of formulations.

KEYWORDS: Nanotechnology, Applications, Therapeutic efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is the science that deals with the processes that occur at molecular level and of nanolength scale size. The word nano($1\text{nm}=10^{-9}\text{ m}$) is derived from Latin word, which means 'dwarf'. Nanotechnology is a multidisciplinary field, convergence of basic sciences and applied disciplines like biophysics, molecular biology, and bioengineering. It has created powerful impact in various fields of medicine including cardiology, ophthalmology, endocrinology, oncology, pulmonology, immunology etc., and to highly specialized areas like gene delivery, brain targeting, tumor targeting, and oral vaccine formulations.

Nanotechnology provides two basic types of nanotools i.e nanomaterials and nanodevices, which play a key role in realm of pharmaceutical nanotechnology and related fields. In pharmacy size reduction plays an important role in formulation development as drugs in nanometer size range enhance performance in a variety of dosage forms. Nanotechnology is related to design characterization, production and applications of structures, devices and systems by controlling size and shape at nanometer scale for better pharmaceutical applications.

Nanoscale technology^[1] improves therapeutic efficacy of drugs by:

- Increasing surface area
- Improving solubility of hydrophobic drugs
- Improving permeability or transport of poorly permeable drugs (class III and IV drugs as per the Biopharmaceutical Classification System [BCS])
- Reducing frequency of dose administration
- Preventing degradation of drugs in physiological milieu
- Modulating biodistribution and drug disposition of drugs
- Enhancing oral bioavailability
- Rapid onset of therapeutic action
- Enabling targeted delivery of the drugs to the site of action.

Classification of nanotechnology^[2]

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of various types of pharmaceutical nanosystems.

Nanocrystals

Nanocrystals are nanoparticles with nanometer size range with crystalline character. One of the characteristic feature of nanocrystals is that they are composed of 100% drug without any carrier material. Dispersion of drug nanocrystals in liquid media leads to “nanosuspensions”. In general the dispersed particles need to be stabilized, by surfactants or polymeric stabilizers. Dispersion media can be water, aqueous solutions or nonaqueous media (eg, liquid polyethylene glycol [PEG], oils). Nanocrystals possess advantages of increase in saturation solubility and increased bioavailability due to increase of dissolution velocity by surface enlargement. Some of the marketed products of nanocrystals are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of current state of development of drugs using Nanocrystal[®] technology.^[1]

Trade name	Drug	Indication	Company	Status
Emend [®]	Aprepitant	Anti emetic	Merck	Marketed
Tricor [®]	Fenofibrate	Hypercholesterolemia	Abbott	Marketed
Nucryst [®]	Silver	Anti bacterial	Nucryst Pharmaceuticals	Phase II
Semapimod [®]	Guanylhyazone	TNF- α inhibitor	Cytokine Pharmasciences	Phase II
Paxceed [®]	Paclitaxel	Anti inflammatory	Angiotech	Phase III

Nanosuspensions

Nanosuspensions can be defined as colloidal dispersions of nano-sized particles that are stabilized by a suitable stabilizer. They can also be defined as biphasic systems consisting of pure drug particles dispersed in an aqueous vehicle in which the diameter of the suspended particle is less than 1 μ m in size. Nanosuspensions resolve the problem of poor bioavailability

by enhancing the solubility and permeability across the membranes. Some of the marketed products of nanosuspensions are shown in Table 2.

Nanosuspensions possess advantages^[6]

- 1) Increase in the dissolution velocity and saturation solubility of the drug
- 2) Improved biological performance
- 3) Ease of manufacture and scale-up
- 4) Long-term physical stability
- 5) Versatility
- 6) Increase in the oral absorption
- 7) Improved dose proportionality

Table 2: Overview of current state of development of drugs using Nanosuspension[®] technology.^[4]

Trade name	Drug	Indication	Company	Status
Rapammune [®]	Rapamycin	Immunosuppressant	Pfizer	Marketed
Invega Sustenna [®]	Paliperidone palmitate	Anti-schizophrenia	Johnson and Johnson	Phase III
Megace [®] ES	Megestrol acetate	Steroid hormone	Par pharmaceutical	Marketed
TriCor [®]	Fenofibrate	Hypo-lipidemic	Abbott	Marketed
Emend [®]	Eprepitant (Oral)	Anti-emetic	Merck	Marketed

Nanoparticles

Nanoparticles are defined as particles less than 100nm in diameter that exhibit new or enhanced size-dependent properties compared with larger particles of the same material. Polymeric nanoparticles include both vesicular systems (nanocapsules) and matrix systems (nanospheres).

Table 3: Overview of current state of development of drugs using Nanoparticle[®] technology.^[5]

Trade name	Drug	Indication	Company	Status
Rapammune [®]	Rapamycin	Immunosuppressant	Wyeth	Marketed
Emend [®]	Aprepitant	Anti-emetic	Merck	Marketed
Avinza [®]	Morphine sulphate	Phycostimulant	King pharmaceuticals	Marketed
Ritalin	Methyphenidate Hcl	CNS stimulant	Novartis	Marketed
Auroshell	Gold coated silica nanoparticles	Solid tumors	Nanospectra biosciences	Phase I

Nanocapsules are the systems in which the drug is confined to a cavity surrounded by unique polymeric membrane whereas **nanospheres** are systems in which the drug is dispersed through out the polymer matrix. The various natural polymers like gelatin, albumin and

alginate are used to prepare the nanoparticles. Polymeric nanoparticulate systems are attractive modules for intracellular and site specific delivery. Nanoparticles can be made to reach a target site by virtue of their size and surfacemodification with a specific recognition ligand. Their surface can be easily modified and functionalized.

Nanoemulsions may be defined as oil-in-water (O/W), water- in-oil (w/o) emulsions with mean droplet diameters ranging from 50 to 1000nm. Usually, the average droplet size is between 100 and 500 nm. The particles can exist as water-in-oil and oil in-water forms, where the core of particle is either water or oil, respectively.

Table 4: Overview of current state of development of drugs using Nanoemulsion[®] technology.^[2]

Trade Name	Drug	Indication	Company	Status
Liple	Palmitate alprostadil	Vasodilator	Mitsubishi pharmaceutical	Marketed
Limethason	Dexamethasone	Steroid	Mitsubishi pharmaceutical	Marketed
Diprivan	Propofol	Anaesthetic	Astra Zeneca	Marketed
Ropion	Flurbiprofenaxtil	NSAID	Kaken pharmaceutical,	Marketed
Restasis [®]	Cyclosporine	Ophthalmic eye drops	Allergan	Marketed

Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs)

These are new generation of submicron-sized lipid emulsions where the liquid lipid (oil) has been substituted by a solid lipid. SLNs offer unique properties such as small size, large surface area, high drug loading and the interaction of phases at the interfaces, and are attractive for their potential to improve performance of pharmaceuticals, Nutraceuticals and other materials.

Solid lipid nanoparticles provide following advantages^{8, 9}:

- 1) Control and target drug release
- 2) Improves the stability of pharmaceuticals
- 3) High and enhanced drug content when compared to other carriers
- 4) Feasibility of carrying both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs
- 5) Water based technology
- 6) Easy to scale-up and sterilize
- 7) Good biocompatibility & Low toxicity

9) SLNs in the range of 120- 200nm are not taken up readily by the cells of the reticulo endothelial system and thus bypass liver and spleen filtration.

Carbon Nanoparticles

The unique properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) such as their high surface to volume ratios, enhanced conductivity and strength, biocompatibility, ease of functionalization, optical properties, etc.) have led to their consideration to serve as novel drug and gene delivery carriers. They are effectively taken up by many different cell types through several mechanisms. CNTs have acted as carriers of anticancer molecules, anti-inflammatory drugs, steroids, etc.

Table 5: Overview of current state of development of drugs using NanoTube® technology.^[2]

Trade Name	Drug	Indication	Company / Institution	Status
None	Doxorubicin–CNT	Breast, liver & solid tumors	MIT, Rice University, Chinese Academy of Sciences	Preclinical
None	Paclitaxel–CNT	Breast & ovarian cancer	NCI-supported labs	Preclinical
None	Cisplatin–CNT	Solid tumors	University of Trieste	Preclinical
None	CNT–siRNA system	Gene therapy (oncology)	Rice University	Preclinical

Metallic Nanoparticles

(Gold nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles, iron oxide nanoparticles, etc.)

Metal-based nanosystems are emerging anti-tumor nanosystems with high clinical application value. From the perspective of drug delivery, the adjustable size and shape of metal-based nanosystems provide flexibility in nanosystem optimization. Metal-based nanosystems with inherent therapeutic effects have simple pharmacological designs. In addition, compared to traditional drug-loaded nanosystems, self-therapeutic metal-based nanosystems are cheaper and more clinically translatable.

Table 6: Overview of current state of development of drugs using Metallic Nano Based® technology.^[2]

Trade Name	Drug	Indication	Company / Institution	Status
AuroShell®	Gold nanoshell-mediated photothermal therapy	Solid tumors	Nanospectra Biosciences	Phase I/II clinical trials
None	Gold nanoparticle–doxorubicin	Breast cancer	University of Missouri	Preclinical
None	Gold nanoparticle vaccine adjuvants	Infectious diseases	NIH-funded labs	Preclinical
None	Silver nanoparticles	Antibacterial coatings, wound care	Various companies	Commercial products, not drugs
Ferumoxytol	Iron-oxide nanoparticles	Iron-deficiency anemia	AMAG Pharmaceuticals	Approved (but not

(Feraheme®)		(also used as MRI contrast – off-label)		CNT/QD-related)
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Silicon Nanoparticles

Mesoporous silica is a white powder with non-toxic, odorless, non-polluting, high purity, low density, large specific surface area, etc. It has excellent stability and enhancement properties. Currently, mesoporous silica has been involved in a number of fields, including plastics, rubber, coatings, fibers and biomedicine. Due to its porous nature, mesoporous silica can adsorb and hold a large number of drug molecules, and is often used as a delivery vehicle for active molecules in drug delivery. Silica nanoparticles can also be coupled with drugs to form ultra-small nanoparticle C'Dot drug conjugate (CDC) platforms. Small size and easy surface modification facilitate deeper penetration into solid tumors and deliver large amounts of toxic payloads.

Table 7: Overview of current state of development of drugs using Silicon Nano-Based® technology.^[5]

Trade Name	Drug/Payload	Indication	Company / Institution	Status
None	Porous silicon–doxorubicin	Cancer (solid tumors)	University of California, San Diego	Preclinical
None	Silicon nanoparticle vaccine carriers	Viral & cancer vaccines	Several academic groups	Preclinical
None	Silicon QD–drug conjugates	Imaging + therapy	Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology	Preclinical
None	Silica nanoparticle platforms (e.g., mesoporous silica)	Drug delivery	Multiple biotech groups	Preclinical–early research

Quantum Dots (QD)-Based Drug/Imaging/Theranostics

Quantum dots (QDs), also known as nanoscale semiconductor crystals, are nanoparticles with unique optical and electronic properties such as bright and intensive fluorescence. Since most conventional organic label dyes do not offer the near-infrared (>650 nm) emission possibility, QDs, with their tunable optical properties, have gained a lot of interest. They possess characteristics such as good chemical and photo-stability, high quantum yield and size-tunable light emission. The controlled release of therapeutic agents is not only permitted by the integration of QDs into drug delivery vehicles but synchronous diagnostic imaging is also enabled, thereby transversing the gap between therapy and diagnostics (theranostics). The principles of QD design and biofunctionalization that are critical for minimizing toxicity and enhancing biocompatibility are explored.

Table 8: Overview of current state of development of drugs using Quantum Dots (QD)-Based Drug® technology.5

Trade Name	Drug/Payload	Indication	Company / Institution	Status
None	QD–doxorubicin	Cancer therapy + imaging	Korea Institute of Science & Technology	Preclinical
None	QD–siRNA nanocarriers	Gene-targeted cancer therapy	University of Toronto	Preclinical
None	QD-based lymph node tracers	Breast cancer staging	Multiple research institutions	Preclinical
None	QD–antibody conjugates	Tumor identification	Invitrogen / Thermo Fisher	Research use (not therapeutic)

Future Directions

Future nanomedicine research will focus on precision targeting, personalized therapy, and biodegradable materials. Emerging technologies, such as exosome-mimetic nanoparticles and bioinspired carriers, show promise for gene and protein delivery.^[12] Collaboration between academia, industry, and regulatory bodies will be key for translating laboratory innovation into safe therapeutics.

CONCLUSION

Nanotechnology continues to reshape drug development by bridging molecular science and clinical translation. Recent years have witnessed remarkable success stories, notably in vaccine development and targeted drug delivery. However, consistent manufacturing practices, standardized toxicity evaluation, and clearer regulatory frameworks are necessary for sustainable progress. The convergence of nanotechnology with AI, genomics, and precision medicine is expected to define the next decade of pharmaceutical innovation.

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